

MEDICAL AND BIOLOGICAL STUDIES OF MEAT POLYCOMPONENT PRODUCTS BASED ON REGIONAL RAW MATERIALS

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the study of the medical and biological safety of consumption of multicomponent meat-rich semi-finished products and semi-smoked sausage. When creating functional products, the approach of multi-ingredient modeling of the future product is applied according to the principle of adding nutritional and biological value. The multi-component nature of the constituent ingredients with different chemical composition makes it possible to obtain products with specified characteristics. There is a problem of ensuring the food safety of the developed product during production, storage and consumption of finished products.

The purpose of the study was to study the effect of the developed meat-containing polycomponent semi-finished products and semi-smoked sausage on the growth dynamics and the level of metabolic processes of experimental rats when they are introduced into the standard diets of animals in the amount of 30 %. The work was performed on 36 white non-linear rats weighing 160–200 g.

Medical and biological studies of multicomponent meat-containing products have shown their absence of a negative effect on the growth and development of animals, the level of metabolic processes during the growth period.

It has been established, that feeding rats with meat-rich polycomponent products in the amount of 30 % of the standard diet increases the live weight of rats by 33–38 % within 3 weeks. Anatomopathological changes in the internal organs of the experimental rats were not detected.

The inclusion of meat-rich multicomponent products in the diet of rats promotes the strengthening of hematological processes in the body, increases the concentration of erythrocytes in the blood to $8.01 \pm 0.11 \cdot 10^{12}/l$, which is 12.7 % higher, compared to the con-

trol animals, increases the hemoglobin content in erythrocytes by 45.83–58.33 % higher, compared to the control animals.

It has been proven, that the consumption of meat-containing multicomponent products by rats leads to an increase in the concentration of total protein by 4.79 %, hemoglobin by 42.12 %, and creatinine by 19.68 %. Enhanced protein synthesis due to intensification of catabolism leads to an increase in bilirubin concentration by 19.12–21.97 % compared to the control rats.

Keywords: meat products, safety, live weight dynamics, biochemical parameters, experimental rats.

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1. Introduction

Human nutrition can be attributed to the branch of medicine, which is based on the biochemical interaction of food products with the human body. The phenotypic transition from a healthy state to a disease state can be attributed to changes in genes and/or protein expression. Recently, an indirect relationship between the type and nature of the diet and the full realization of the genetic potential of each individual has been proven. Personalized dietary nutrition, which takes into account the patient's genetic predisposition to non-infectious metabolic diseases, has become widely popular in this regard [1–3]. Personalized nutrition prevents the development of many diseases that are stimulated by hypodynamism, improper nutrition, alcohol abuse and, in general, an unhealthy lifestyle [4, 5].

The implementation of personalized nutrition, taking into account medical indications, led to the development of a whole direction in the food industry for the production of functional food products.

When creating functional products, the approach of multi-ingredient modeling of the future product is applied according to the principle of adding nutritional and biological value. Therefore, the main principle of developing a functional product is the multicomponent nature of the constituent ingredients and their biological availability to proteolytic enzymes [6]. It is the combination of nutrients of different origin, with different biological value and digestibility that makes it possible to obtain products with given characteristics.

Functional food or nutraceuticals is a new trend in food science. The use of nutraceuticals for the treatment of human diseases has become a popular topic of research recently. Functional products contain bioactive ingredients that contribute to human physiological development and help fight chronic diseases. Most pharmacological synthetic drugs have side effects that can negatively affect human health. On the other hand, functional food can provide natural cures for most human diseases and can also prevent them by boosting the body's immune system. Nutraceuticals have proven their effectiveness against cancer, tumors, diabetes, obesity, high blood pressure, premature aging, blood detoxification, etc. [7–9]. Gradually, pharmaceuticals are shifting towards nutraceuticals to find natural cures for all health related problems. Different types of fruits, vegetables, fish oil, nutritional supplements and phytochemicals can act as functional food.

At the same time, there is a problem of creating not only an effective, healthy product, but ensuring its food safety during production, storage and consumption of finished products.

Therefore, the purpose of our study was to study the effect of the developed meat-containing polycomponent semi-finished products and semi-smoked sausage on the growth dynamics and metabolic processes of experimental rats when they are introduced into standard animal diets.

2. Materials and Methods

In order to identify the compliance of the characteristics of the developed meat products with the physiological matrix of the designed object, a series of experimental works was conducted on warm-blooded test objects – 30 sexually mature white non-linear rats (males) with an initial weight of 145–150 g, in the conditions of the Romen Interdistrict Veterinary Laboratory of Sumy region (Ukraine). Control and two experimental groups of laboratory animals of 10 individuals each were formed. Groups of animals were formed by the method of random sampling, taking into account body weight as a determining indicator. The animals were quarantined and acclimatized in the vivarium for 14 days. The tested product was administered in an amount of 30 % of the main standard diet (**Table 1**).

The work was performed on 36 white non-linear rats weighing 160–200 g. Keeping and all other manipulations with animals were carried out in compliance with the standards of the European Convention on the Protection of Animals, adopted by the First National Congress of Ukraine on Bioethics, manipulations with animals were carried out in accordance with the European Convention “On the Protection of Vertebrate Animals, which are used for experimental and scientific purposes” dated 18.03.1986 and EU Directive No. 109 dated 24.11.1986, “General ethical principles of animal experiments”, adopted by the First National Congress on Bioethics in Kyiv in 2001 and “Scientific and practical recommendations for keeping laboratory animals and working with them” [10, 11].

The slaughter and bleeding procedure was carried out, taking into account the ethical approaches and rules, established by the UN “World Charter of Nature” (1982) and in accordance with the Law of Ukraine “On the Protection of Animals from Cruelty” dated 02.21.2006.

All groups of animals were kept in standard vivarium conditions with observance of a 12-hour light/dark regime with unlimited access to drinking water and feed (**Fig. 1**).

Fig. 1. Conditions for keeping experimental animals

The animals received a standard complete balanced granulated compound feed for laboratory rats, which provided the physiological needs of their body in vitamins, microelements, minerals and energy. In the experimental groups of rats, 30 % minced meat of the developed combined products (chopped semi-finished products and semi-smoked sausages) was added to the main feed. The recipes of semi-finished products and semi-smoked sausages are given in **Tables 1, 2**.

In order to avoid the effects of random factors on the results of further biochemical and hematological studies, all animals were housed in the same conditions.

Table 1

Recipe of chopped semi-finished products for clinical studies on laboratory rats

Constituent components	Amount, kg or g for 100 kg
Silver crucian carp (minced), kg	30.5
Duck meat, kg	30.5
Wheat bread, kg	12.0
Breadcrumbs, kg	4.0
Onions, kg	1.5
Chicken eggs, kg	2.0
Ground pepper, kg	0.06
Table salt, kg	1.2
Water for soaking bread, kg	18.3
Rosemary extract, kg	0.15

During the experiments, the general condition of the animals, feed and water consumption was monitored daily; body weight was determined once a week.

When analyzing the habit of rats, noted the liveliness of temperament, natural prostration of the body, average fatness. Radical changes in appearance and behavior were not recorded. The fur was quite thick, shiny and characteristic of this species of animal in a normal physiological state,

the claws were not deformed, hard. The body temperature of animals of all groups was normal (37–38 °C), the frequency of respiratory movements was 85–90 per minute. However, it should be noted, that already after the first 7 days of research, the appetite and fur condition of the animals in the experimental groups improved. At the end of the experiment (on the 22nd day), the animals of the experimental groups were distinguished by thicker and shinier fur in comparison with the control ones.

Table 2

Recipe of semi-smoked sausages for clinical studies on laboratory rats

Constituent components	Amount, kg or g for 100 kg
Duck meat, kg	50
Minced fish (silver carp meat), kg	30
Side fat, kg	10
Soy isolate, kg	4
Hemp protein, kg	6
Table salt, g	2874
Sugar sand, g	100
Black pepper, g	100
Sodium nitrite, g	5
Ground nutmeg or coriander, g	50
Fresh peeled garlic, g	200
Cranberry extract, kg	0.2

Feeding was carried out strictly at the same time every day, the usual daily ration did not change. In almost all groups, larger individuals started eating feed first, followed by all others. The experimental groups first ate meat products, and then began the usual diet (**Table 3**).

Table 3

Structure of the daily diet of the experimental groups of rats

Rat group	Number, un.	Daily diet composition
Control	10	complete balanced granulated compound feed
Experiment 1	10	complete balanced granulated compound feed + 30 % minced of semi-finished products
Experiment 2	10	complete balanced granulated compound feed + 30 % of minced sausage

Complete feed for animals includes cereals (oats, wheat, barley, triticale, corn, millet) up to 60 %; legumes – peas, soybeans, lupins are added to compound feed in an amount of up to 35 %. Legumes are added to compound feed after extrusion, micronization, roasting and other heat treatment. The content of vegetable fats in the feed mixture is from 15 to 25 %. The feed mixture is balanced according to essential amino acids – lysine, cystine+methionine, tryptophan, threonine. A mandatory element of a complete compound feed is mineral supplements, including rock salt, magnesium sulfate, disodium phosphate, potassium iodide, calcium carbonate; vitamin supplements – vitamins E, A, thiamin, vitamin B₁₂. Biostimulants are also part of the complete feed: antioxidants, sorbents, probiotics and prebiotics, enzymes, algae, mud, sapropel.

Throughout the experiment, the water used was observed and measured. The control group consumed 17–21 % more water than the animals of the experimental groups. At the same time, the animals behaved actively, had a good appetite, and were not afraid of humans. During the observation period, the fur of the animals in the research groups changed more intensively and became shinier, the nose and paws were pink, the eyes were clean.

The study of the parameters of the blood serum of the animals was carried out dynamically every 7 days of the experiment (on the 7th, 14th and 21st days).

To carry out blood tests with the help of biochemical and hematological analyzers, blood was collected by the method of tail vein puncture. To do this, the tail was heated with warm water, and after disinfection, a vein was pinched near the edge of the tail, a needle was inserted into the vessel and the required amount of blood was extracted with a syringe.

To obtain plasma, blood was collected in tubes with a pre-introduced anticoagulant (1 % heparin solution). Plasma was separated by centrifugation at 1500 rpm for 15 min. After the blood was taken, it was analyzed on an automatic hematological analyzer no later than in 2 hours.

The determination of hematological indicators, namely the total number of leukocytes, the total number of erythrocytes, the hemoglobin content, the number of platelets was performed on an automatic hematological analyzer (Orphée Mythic 18, Switzerland) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Automatic hematology analyzer Orphée Mythic 18 (Switzerland)

The color index (CI) indicates the hemoglobin content in erythrocytes. It is determined based on a blood test for the content of erythrocytes and hemoglobin according to the following formula:

$$CI=3\times Hb/Er,$$

where *Hb* – hemoglobin content in g/l, *Er* – number of erythrocytes, measured in 1 μ l of blood.

The statistical processing of the results was carried out with the help of a standard package of Microsoft Excel programs. A difference was considered probable if the value of $p<0.05$.

3. Results

For the medical-biological assessment of the effect of the developed semi-finished products and semi-smoked sausages on the dynamics of growth and development of the experimental rats, measurements of the live weight of rats during the experiment and a pathological autopsy of the animals after the end of the experiment were carried out.

At the beginning of the experiment, the average live weight of animals in all groups was practically the same and fluctuated at the level of 151.47–159.63 g. The difference between individuals was unreliable. On the 7th day of the experiment, a small difference was observed between the average live weight of animals in the control group and the experimental group, which increased at the end of the experimental period. Thus, the average live weight of rats from the control group at the end of the experiment was 187.5 ± 7.31 g, and in the experimental groups – 209.31–213.99 g, which is 11.63–14.13 % more compared to the control. Accordingly, the absolute increase in the experimental groups was also higher and amounted to 54.27–57.84 g against 31.37 g in the control animals. That is, the relative increase in the animals of the experimental groups was almost a third of the starting live weight of the animals – 33.96–38.18 %. The positive effect on the growth dynamics in rats is explained by the presence of protein of mainly animal origin in the functional research products, balanced in terms of amino acid composition [12, 13].

The anatomical and morphological examination of the internal condition of rats did not reveal pathologies of internal organs. The internal organs were without visible pathological and anatomical changes. The blood had a normal dark red color, it coagulated quickly, without delays. The lungs were light pink. The liver and kidneys corresponded in size and color. The heart also had its proper shape and color, without any deviations. The entire digestive system did not have any visible pathologies, without gastroenterological phenomena. That is, the functional products, introduced into the diet, did not contain any harmful substances and did not have a negative effect on the condition of the animals that consumed these products for 3 weeks.

It is known, that the optimal growth and development of animals requires a complete and balanced feed in terms of all nutrients and essential substances, which ensures their health and productivity. The main macro- and micronutrients play a central role in the functioning of the animal's metabolome and participate in the formation and development of internal tissues and organs [14, 15].

During the study of blood morphology, it was established, that the number of red and white blood cells in animals of all groups was within the normal range during the entire experiment. However, a tendency to an increase in the number of erythrocytes was noted in rats that consumed meat-rich polycomponent semi-smoked sausage along with the diet. The concentration of erythrocytes in the blood of these rats was $8.01 \pm 0.11 \cdot 10^{12}/l$, which is 12.66 % higher, compared to the control animals. It has been proven, that the consumption of meat and vegetable food optimizes the composition of red and white blood cells and stimulates the formation of erythrocytes in the bone marrow [16, 17]. It has been established, that the modification of the diet increases the hemoglobin content in erythrocytes by 45.83–58.33 % compared to the control animals.

The analysis of the biochemical composition of the blood of the experimental rats showed that during the experiment, the level of total protein, hemoglobin, and creatinine in the blood of the experimental rats increased, which indicates an increase in protein metabolism. Thus, the concentration of total blood plasma protein in the control animals at the end of the experiment was $71.58 \pm 0.39 \text{ g/dm}^3$, which is 3.74–4.79 % lower compared to the experimental animals of groups 1 and 2. The results of the hemoglobin content study prove that the increase in the level of total protein occurred due to this respiratory protein. The average concentration of hemoglobin in the blood of the experimental animals at the end of the experiment was 17.77 g/dm^3 , which is 46.94 % higher, compared to rats in the control group that consumed the standard diet. That is, the increase in balanced protein, the source of which was multi-ingredient functional meat-containing products, led to the intensification of protein synthesis in the animal body. It was the essential amino acids present in the developed products that stimulated the strengthening of anabolic processes in the red bone marrow and other organs [18].

It was established, that the concentration of creatinine in the blood increased in rats that received meat-containing products of multicomponent composition. At the end of the experiment, its level in the experimental groups was 73.09–73.21 mol/dm^3 , which is 19.68 % higher, compared to the control group. There was also a tendency to increase the level of creatinine compared to the first days of the experiment, which can be explained by the increase in protein and energy metabolism [19, 20].

The study of the level of bilirubin, a product of the breakdown of heme pigments, showed that the metabolism of these compounds was accelerated in the experimental rats. At the end of the experiment, the concentration of total bilirubin in the blood of the experimental animals was 1.09–1.11 $\mu\text{mol/dm}^3$, which is 20.55 % higher, compared to the control animals. The metabolism of heme pigments can increase within physiological norms as a result of enhanced hemolysis of erythrocytes and, accordingly, prior synthesis of mainly hemoglobin [21].

The introduction of the developed products with the high protein content, but low lipid content was predicted to have no effect on the level of cholesterol in the blood of the experimental animals. However, a decrease in blood glucose was observed in the experimental rats, the concentration of which was 3.79–4.03 mmol/dm^3 at the end of the experiment. Meat-rich mul-

ticomponent products do not contain a significant amount of polysaccharides, compared to the standard diet, so their introduction into the diet of rats in the amount of 30 % does not lead to an increase in the level of glucose, circulating in the blood.

4. Conclusions

The medical-biological studies of the multicomponent meat-containing products showed the absence of a negative effect on the growth and development of animals, the level of metabolic processes during the growth period.

It has been established, that feeding rats with meat-rich polycomponent products in the amount of 30 % of the standard diet increases the live weight of rats by 33–38 % within 3 weeks. Anatomopathological changes in the internal organs of the experimental rats were not detected.

The inclusion of meat-rich multicomponent products in the diet of rats promotes the strengthening of hematological processes in the body, increases the concentration of erythrocytes in the blood to $8.01 \pm 0.11 \cdot 10^{12}/l$, which is 12.7 % higher, compared to the control animals, increases the hemoglobin content in erythrocytes by 45.83–58.33 % higher, compared to the control animals.

It has been proven, that the consumption of meat-containing multicomponent products by rats leads to an increase in the concentration of total protein by 4.79 %, hemoglobin by 42.12 %, and creatinine by 19.68 %. Enhanced protein synthesis due to intensification of catabolism leads to an increase in bilirubin concentration by 19.12–21.97 % compared to the control rats.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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